

Evaluation of Hospital Management System at Combined Military Hospital Lahore

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To evaluate HMS in terms of user satisfaction, time management, data retrieval, record keeping, confidentiality in terms of medical records and comparison of user preference according to job description.

Study Design: Cross sectional study.

Place of Study: Combined Military Hospital Lahore, from 1st Dec to 31st March 2018.

Methodology: All doctors and hospital personnel using HMS for more than 6 months in CMH Lahore were included by means of non-probability convenient sampling. The total sample size was of 200 participants. Questionnaire was filled regarding user satisfaction, time management, data retrieval, record keeping, confidentiality in terms of medical records and comparison of user preference according to job description and results were analyzed using SPSS 20.

Results: Out of a total of 200 participants, 58 (29%) were satisfied while 142 (71%) were dissatisfied with HMS mostly due to system hang-ups (34.5%) which were observed while using this software. Out of the total respondents, 133 (66.5%) participants believed it increased time spent per patient mostly due to too much information being present on patient encounter form (28%), and 66 (33%) participants were wary of its confidentiality. 142 (71%) participants believed that manual records needed to be kept alongside HMS. However, 141 (70.5%) thought it is an efficient tool for data retrieval, and 156 (78%) believed it to be reliable software.

Conclusion: Most personnel- young and old-were largely dissatisfied with HMS, even though it is believed to be reliable and an efficient tool for data retrieval. Many would still keep manual records and were wary of its confidentiality.

Key words: Hospital, Patient information management, User satisfaction, Medical record.

INTRODUCTION

HMS is a massive, integrated system that supports the comprehensive information requirements of hospitals, including patient, clinical, ancillary and financial management.¹ It is a computer based system in which data are stored in a database, from where it is put at the disposal of authorized users.² Hospitals consists of different departments which work together to provide services to the patients.³

Modern HMS is an integrated system that manages data related to clinic, laboratory, pharmacy, radiology and finance departments. Information and management systems are used in hospitals to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of the hospitals in modern world. This system comprises of a set of related modules which are used to collect, reclaim, stock and distribute data which helps in improving patient care.⁴

HMS is a program that currently isn't being widely used in Pakistan. Except a handful of private institutes, majority of the hospitals are still run in an archaic manual manner where human error is inevitable and records are not being properly kept. However, amidst all this, Pakistan Army is providing health care services not only to defense forces personnel but also to civilians. Army Medical Corps (AMC) decided to adopt HMS in

all military hospitals.⁴ Instillation of this system in CMH Lahore is one such initiative.

The aim of this study was to evaluate HMS in CMH Lahore in terms of its user's satisfaction, time management, data retrieval, record keeping, and confidentiality of medical record. It is also used to evaluate and compare which grade of users was most satisfied with HMS. It is believed that quality of services can be improved through this due to quick data retrieval, obtaining accurate, comprehensive history and even providing steps for appropriate management. Information system quality is categorized into six major dimensions that include system quality, information quality, use, user satisfaction, individual impact and organizational impact.⁵

In general, one can define hospital information systems as comprehensive software for patient information integration, and to exchange comprehensive patient information between wards and other medical centers/departments in order to expedite the process of patient care, improve quality, increase patient satisfaction and reduce cost.⁶

It is as an integrated information system which improves patient care by increasing the user's knowledge and reducing uncertainty allowing rational decisions to be made from the information provided.⁶

METHODOLOGY

A cross-sectional study, using a specially designed

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questionnaire was adopted to explore the perceptions of HMS users at Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Lahore. Primary data was collected from 1st December 2017 to 31st March 2018. A total of 200 doctors and administrators, both male and female, between 25 and 55 years of age having access to the HMS for more than six months were included in the study by means of non-probability convenient sampling technique. Doctors not using HMS were excluded from this study.

Permission from the hospital ethical committee and college administrations was obtained prior to collecting the primary data. A printed questionnaire was given to each participant after the verbal consent of the participant and was filled there and then. All participants were reassured about the confidentiality of the filled forms. The questionnaire included the demographic data i.e. age, gender, designation and specialty of the participant. Information regarding user satisfaction, reason for dissatisfaction, time management, data retrieval, manual record keeping and confidentiality of medical records was collected.

Data collected was analyzed using SPSS version 20.0. Chi square test was applied at 95% confidence interval. The p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The results were then interpreted and discussed.

RESULTS

Gender, age, designation and specialty of the respondents are shown in Table 1.0. General user satisfaction is shown in Fig. 1.0

Satisfaction, reasons for dissatisfaction and time management are shown in Table 2.0

User satisfaction according to designation, data retrieval in timely manner, manual record keeping and confidentiality with HMS use are shown in Table 3.0

DISCUSSION

Most of the participants in our study were not satisfied with the current HMS system. As expected with newly

installed software, many users faced trouble with System hang ups, work overload and even software complexity. Since HMS was introduced in CMH Lahore in 2012, many users have raised concerns over the doctor patient imbalance that pertains to the increased workload and decreased time efficiency. The results showed, that majority of the subjects were content with the time spent per patient with HMS. While others, thought that their own lack of proficiency in using the system might be the problem. It is in agreement with the other studies conducted in USA on implementation of electronic health records system which showed that time spent on computers was increased and time and attention given to patient was decreased.^{7,8} Similar percentage of users found there to be too much detail in patient encounter form or that the ergonomics of the office did not support efficiency.

HMS is a tool for efficient and fast data retrieval. These results were in consistent with the results of study conducted by Ford EW et al, which showed importance of electronic medical record for data retrieval and record keeping.⁹ Results confirmed that majority of the users were content with the speed of turnover of patient files whenever HMS was accessed. The others found that their own lack of proficiency or system hang ups were to blame for data retrieval issues. Lack of proficiency can be minimized by providing short crash courses on HMS usage and accessibility. System Hang ups are reducing with every new update to the HMS system. The HMS system requires updates and improvements as revealed by the study. The users were dissatisfied with the recurrent system hang-ups and complexity of the system. HMS software should be reviewed and updated often so as to decrease this dissatisfaction among the users. Many users agreed that despite the computerization of patient data, manual records of all input into the system should be kept along with using HMS. Some opinions stated that they are more comfortable writing down patient information than typing it out because purely HMS removes the familiarity between the doctor and patient; An important rapport to establish as good practicing

Table 1.0: Distribution of participants according to gender, age and designation.

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	92	46.0
Female	108	54.0
Age (years)	Frequency	Percent
21-35	161	80.5
35-55	39	19.5
Designation	Frequency	Percent
Senior Consultants	21	10.5
Consultants	31	15.5
Trainees	61	30.5
Administrators	10	5.0
House Officers	77	38.5

Fig. 1.0 HMS User Satisfaction

Table 2

HMS User Satisfaction	Frequency	Percent	p-value
Yes	57	28.5	p=0.021
No	143	71.5	
No (Due to Workload)	55	27.5	
No (Due to Software Complexity)	19	9.5	
No (Due to System Hangups)	69	34.5	
Total	200	100.0	
Increase in Time spent per Patient	Frequency	Percent	p-value
Yes	133	66.5	p=0.064
Yes (Due to too much detail in patient encounter form)	56	28.0	
Yes (Due to Lack in proficiency in computer usage)	38	19.0	
Yes (Due to ergonomics of office)	39	19.5	
No	67	33.5	
Total	200	100.0	

Table 3

User Satisfaction according to Designation	Frequency	Percent	p-value
Yes			p=0.224
Senior Consultant	9	4.5	
Consultant	8	4.0	
Trainee	15	7.5	
Administrator	7	3.5	
House Officer	19	9.5	
No			
Senior Consultant	12	6.0	
Consultant	23	11.5	
Trainee	46	23.0	
Administrator	3	1.5	
House Officer	58	29.0	
Total	200	100.0	
HMS as an Efficient Tool for Data Retrieval	Frequency	Percent	p-value
Yes	141	70.5	p=0.180
No	59	29.5	
Total	200	100.5	
Retaining Manual Record along with Electronic Record	Frequency	Percent	p-value
Yes	142	71.0	p=0.040
No	58	29.0	
Total	200	100.0	
Reliability of HMS for Record Keeping	Frequency	Percent	p-value
Yes	156	78.0	p=0.057
No	44	22.0	
Total	200	100.0	
Concerns regarding Patient's Confidentiality	Frequency	Percent	p-value
Yes	66	33.0	p=0.686
No	134	67.0	
Total	200	100.0	

Physicians. They want to spend more time on the patient than entering data into the computer. In an editorial titled "Survival of the kindest" Safdar CA has stressed on listening to the patients attentively rather than filling the forms on HMS.¹⁰ Ergonomics of the office should be looked into to improve the doctor-patient relationship with HMS usage. The use of electronic pens and voice recorders can help minimize this issue. They also explored that manual records are a fail safe way of data storage. The others said that with a computer system there was no need to increase time spent per patient by doing a write up and also entering data into HMS. When a patient does not bring his past medical records with him to the hospital, HMS has been seen as a quick way of accessing those important histories.

Confidentiality is of utmost importance between doctors, patients and their colleagues. Our study is in accordance to the one conducted by CMH Peshawar, that showed similar results indicating that HMS reduces chances of confidentiality breaches. As HMS can only be accessed by authorised personnel and administrators, patient information and records are much more safe than manual records that can be misplaced and accessed by all. A study by Fernandez- Aleman et al has elaborated that information technology should be used responsibly by it users to protect patient confidentiality.¹¹

Concerning satisfaction with HMS according to Job description, it was found that most senior consultants preferred the old method of manual records to the new HMS setup. Their complaints were mainly lack of proficiency and disruption in rapport of doctor and patient. The young staff who was taking part in the survey were not in favor of using HMS as it increased the time spent per patient which was surprising as most of them had attended HMS courses to increase their capabilities with the system. Some consultants admitted to allowing their juniors and house officers to fill in the HMS forms so as to prevent error as they lack the skills. Even though the younger age groups that included PG trainees and House officers were clearly more comfortable with the digitization were as dissatisfied as the older groups who were hesitant using this new technology due to lack of familiarity.

This study was in concordance to the study done in CMH Peshawar in 2014. Even though there were some areas where large differences in statistics could be noted, majority of the response remained the same. In both studies, user dissatisfaction was high- 64.5% in Peshawar and 71% in Lahore. Both studies concluded that it was majorly due to the increased time spent per patient- 84% in Peshawar and 66.5% in Lahore. However, both also reached a census on HMS being a good source of data retrieval 80% in Peshawar and 70.5% in Lahore and both believed breach in patient confidentiality was not an issue.

A stark difference that can be seen in both the studies is the difference in perception of whether manual records are to be maintained alongside HMS. In CMH Peshawar 65% believed in not keeping manual records while in CMH Lahore 71% believed it was important to maintain

records alongside this digitalized program. This clearly showed the doubt the staff of CMH Lahore had in HMS.

A major point to be noted while comparing both the studies is the difference in sample size that was taken. The study held in CMH Peshawar had a sample size of mere 71 participants while the one conducted in Lahore had a sample size of 200 participants. This difference brings in to light the uniform dissatisfaction across hospitals, their management and their staff.

Weakness of HMS as a system could be seen throughout the conductance of this study. Moreover, the results reciprocate this. Unfortunately, no tangible solution can be found just by the conducting of this study. More comprehensive surveys and studies should be held to pin point the inherent problem within the system. An open ended questionnaire could be circulated in each department to advice how HMS could be improved in decreasing the time spent per patient and how could they increase its credibility so as to not require retention of the manual records alongside it. A major reason for the vast dissatisfaction was the system hang-ups. Steps must be taken to eliminate this problem as such problems can be tackled by simply installing a better software. Another reason was the system complexity, for this thorough analysis is to be done.

The main limitation of this study was the larger sample size that was required to study the difference between the different variables more exclusively. The variety of participants was too variable for a single center study and results could not be widely generalized. Exclusion criteria was strictly followed to minimize error and to limit the variables as the sample size was small.

CONCLUSION

A vast percentage of doctors were dissatisfied with the use of HMS largely attributing to increase in time spent per patient and due to system hang ups. However, most of the personnel assented that HMS was reliable and its use provided efficient means of data retrieval although they still felt the need for the recording and maintenance of manual records.

On the whole the personnel most acquitted to the use of HMS such as trainees and house officers were the most dissatisfied with its use, as compared to senior personnel such as consultants and senior consultants.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This study has no conflict of interest to declare by any author.

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